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USING INTERACTIVE METHODS EDUCATION

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Annotation. Currently, modern methods of teaching are widely used in the educational process. The use of modern teaching methods can lead to greater effectiveness in teaching. It is advisable to choose these techniques based on the didactic function of each lesson. Enriching the traditional form of teaching with a variety of methods that enhance the learner's performance will lead to an increase in the level of self-learning. This article deals with these problems and, moreover, further examples are provided.

Keywords: Education, learning process, teaching methods, learning process, didactic literature

Today, in a number of developed countries, new methods are called interactive methods, which provide a solid basis for the use of modern teaching technologies that guarantee the effectiveness of the educational process. Interactive teaching methods are among the most widely used in all types of educational institutions. However, there are many types of interactive teaching methods that are available to fulfill almost all of the educational and learning tasks. In practice, they can be used appropriately for a specific purpose. This situation has led to the problem of choosing the right methods of interactive learning for a particular purpose. For this purpose, the organization of the classroom process, the learner's interest in the students, their continued involvement in the learning process, the breakdown of the material into small pieces, and the discovery of their contents appear. Using techniques such as attacking, working in small groups, discussion, problem-solving, referral text, project, role-playing, and encouraging learners to carry out practical exercises independently is very important in interactive teaching. An interactive method is to work together to solve an activity or problem through dialogue, discussion, or debate.

The advantage of this method is that the whole activity prepares students

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for independent thinking independent living. Interactive methods are those that are at the center of the learning process that encourage learners to think and act independently. [1:] When these methods are used, the educator encourages the student to actively participate. The learner is involved throughout the process. The benefits of a student-centered approach are: better learning outcomes; high motivation of the learner; the emphasis on previously acquired knowledge; alignment of the learning process with students' goals and needs; creation of conditions for bilateral feedback. Thus, the use of interactive methods in teaching subjects has a distinctive feature. Careful study and application of each interactive method used in educational practice can increase student thinking and have a positive impact on finding the right solution to the problem. Analyzing various theoretical and practical problems through interactive methods can help students to broaden and deepen their knowledge, skills and abilities. From the above, it is necessary to properly analyze and classify the methods of interactive learning. The following is a general overview of this issue. The classification of these techniques can be divided into interactive methods, interactive learning strategies, and interactive graphic organizers. Currently, the most popular methods of interactive learning are: Interactive methods: "Case-study" (or "Study Cases"), "Bliss-questioning", "Modeling", "Creative work", "Problem-based learning" and others. Interactive learning strategies: "Brainstorm", "Boomerang", "Gallery", "Zig-zag", "Step by Step", "Ice-breaker", "Rotation", "Round snow", etc. The group approach to interactive learning strategies from the content of interactive learning methods is based on the fact that, in a sense, it is a strategic approach. In fact, both of these strategies relate to interactive teaching methods, with no differences between them.

Interactive graphic organizers: "Fish skeleton", "BBB", "Conceptual table", "Venn diagram", "T-table", "Insert", "Cluster", "Why?", Etc. When separating interactive graphic organizers, the main points of these sessions are based on the fact that they are written in different graphical forms. In fact, working with these graphic organizers is more and more related to interactive teaching methods, with no differences between them. Interactive teaching methods are often used in conjunction with various training technologies. Applying these techniques will increase the activity of the participants and improve the effectiveness of their education. [2: pp. 116-120] In this regard, the convenience of some of the current classification methods in the above classification for the use of various types of training technologies is presented in the list below. The convenience of some interactive learning

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methods in this list for using various types of training technologies is more conducive and, in fact, more and more interactive techniques with specific training technologies are given. 1. The technology for teaching secondary school learners: Free writing Essential essay Cluster B-B-B drawing T-drawing 2. Technology for teaching primary school learners: Mental Attack Bliss request Bliss-game Conceptual table 3. The technology for practical training: Tutorial Written and oral roundtable discussions Insert table The "why" drawing The diagram "How?" 4. Independent learning technology: Case study technology Comprehension text writing 5. Technology of project education: Sequenced logical chains, Flower diagram One of the most serious didactic problems is how education choices are concerned. The didactic literature explains the various factors that influence the effectiveness of selecting and applying teaching methods: First, it relates to the didactic goals and objectives of the training sessions; Second, depending on the nature of the material, the topic is presented; Third, it depends on the level of knowledge and development of the trainees; Fourthly, it relates to specific (current) methods of teaching the basics of science studied in the learning process Fifth, it depends on the circumstances of the institution of higher education or the department; [2: pp. 113-127] Thus, the process of school education in higher education institutions is carried out within the framework of a multilateral system organized according to modern forms and methods of teaching. Each form has its own set of tasks, but the combination of forms and methods creates a unique didactic set. The realization of this didactic complex is determined by the psychological and pedagogical regularities of the educational process.

References:

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